

Nonlinear finite element analysis of steel-concrete-steel sandwich wind turbine towers

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Abstract

The increasing height of modern wind turbines encumbers the lower segments of their towers with higher loads and dictates the expansion of tower-base diameters beyond the limits imposed by today's means of transportation. As a potential solution to this issue, the substitution of conventional steel tower sections with sandwich-type ones is herein investigated. The geometry in question, consisting of two tubular steel shells and a concrete core, is expected to enhance the stiffness, load capacity and ductility of the pertinent section with minimal weight and cost addition. In order for the feasibility and efficiency of this concept to be assessed, a downscaled hybrid tower, comprising a sandwich lower segment and a conventional steel upper segment, was modelled within this study by means of finite elements, taking into account the nonlinearity imposed by geometry, materials and layers' interfaces. The model was calibrated and validated according to the behavior of identical specimens, which had been previously constructed and tested for this purpose. A series of parametric analyses was subsequently carried out on the calibrated tower model, based on key factors such as the core's and faces' thicknesses, materials' properties and loading conditions. The results of this investigation are finally discussed and useful conclusions are highlighted.

Keywords: Wind turbine towers, sandwich shells, nonlinear finite element analysis, experimental investigation

1. Introduction

Further improvement in efficiency of wind turbines necessitates towers of increased height and, consequently, larger diameter, particularly at the lower segment, in order for them to withstand the accordingly higher loads. However, transportability eventually becomes more than an issue, as track dimensions, bridge heights and road curves impose a limit to such an enlargement, at least as far as onshore wind turbines are concerned. The concept investigated here, for addressing this issue, involves the substitution of the conventional steel shells at the lower segments of a tower with sandwich-type ones, consisting of two concentric steel shells and a binding core of some lightweight material between them. Such a design is expected to enhance the strength, stiffness, ductility, as well as local-buckling resistance of the tower, with a minimal weight addition. In this study, concrete has been selected as core material due to both its decent mechanical properties and lower cost, compared to other candidate materials such as elastomers or metal foams.

Steel-concrete-steel sandwich members have been thoroughly studied analytically, numerically and experimentally, under various loading conditions. Included in the latter are axial compression, pure bending, exposure to fire, impact loads, blast loads and various combinations of them. In the vast majority of these studies, however, sandwich members are regarded as possible alternatives for either columns or beams. Consequently, their examined geometric characteristics and/or load conditions are limited to such applications, that is, low outer-diameter-to-total-thickness ratios and/or quasi-statically applied loads, respectively. On the other hand, Schaumann [1] suggested that sandwich cross sections be possibly incorporated into wind turbine towers, and tested specimens with geometric proportions

suited this type of structure (higher outer-diameter-to-total-thickness ratio) under axially compressive loads. Even so, as far as this potential application is concerned, a load case including bending loads is yet to be applied on this type of sandwich members, and, more importantly, the dynamic nature of a wind turbine's loads is a crucial factor that has not as yet been taken into account. As a first step in this direction, a steel-concrete-steel sandwich member comprising geometric proportions similar to those of a wind turbine tower and being exposed to bending loads, is numerically studied in this paper. Specifically, a downscaled hybrid tower comprising a sandwich lower segment and a conventional steel upper segment was modelled, with its inner and outer steel shells, concrete core and interfaces being simulated by means of shell, solid and contact finite elements, respectively, and with sophisticated material models being incorporated for the introduction of material non-linearities and the simulation of concrete's complex behavior in particular. The model was calibrated and validated according to the results of pertinent experiments on identical sandwich specimens, conducted as part of previous research work of the authors. A series of parametric analyses is subsequently carried out on the calibrated tower model, based on key factors such as the core's and faces' thicknesses, materials' properties and loading conditions. The results of this investigation are finally discussed and useful conclusions are highlighted.

2. Experiments used for validation

For validation of the numerical simulation use was made of experimental results that had been previously obtained and are reported in detail in [2]. A brief description of this experimental campaign is presented here for completeness.

The sandwich specimens involved in the experimental investigation comprised two concentric tubular steel shells with external diameters of 400 mm and 380 mm, respectively, and thickness of 2 mm each, the empty space between them being filled up with cement-mortar, as a concrete substitute with smaller aggregates, able to flow within the narrow available core space. The two shells were cut from the same steel sheet, then cold rolled and finally welded longitudinally to take a tube shape. The core filler was prepared using a ready-mixed cement-mortar product and was hydraulically pumped into the core, on site, with the help of a vacuum pump.

The specimens were geometry-wise based on the conventional steel ones previously tested by Dimopoulos and Gantes [3], the geometrical proportions of which resembled those of an actual wind turbine tower, downscaled at 10%. This was decided in order for a comparison between sandwich specimens and their conventional steel equivalents to be possible. In this respect, for each sandwich specimen, the thicknesses of the inner and outer steel shells added together were equal to the thickness of the uniform steel shell, incorporated into the previously tested specimens. Subsequently, given the thicknesses of the inner and outer steel shells, the width of the concrete core was selected according to the pertinent methodology suggested by Vernardos and Gantes [4]. The basic geometrical properties of the specimens are presented in Figure 1a. As in [3], the specimen was connected by welded flanges and bolts to a secondary steel shell, at the other (free) end of which the actuator load was exerted. At its base, the specimen was connected, again by welded flanges and bolts, to a third component, comprising a short steel shell welded on a plate, which in turn was bolted to the laboratory's testing frame as for a moment connection to be accomplished. All the components, apart from the sandwich one, were designed to have sufficient overstrength, as to behave elastically throughout the tests. The whole cantilever assembly was positioned horizontally on the testing frame and loaded laterally at its very end. The specimen and testing set-up are shown in Figure 1b. The experiment was executed twice with two identical specimens for verification purposes.

Measurements performed during the experimental procedure can be classified into three categories: displacement measurements by linear variable differential transformers (LVDT) and the load cell itself, reflecting the behavior of the specimen macroscopically, strain measurements by strain gauges, capturing local phenomena, and optical measurements by video cameras, depicting the deforming progress. The latter were positioned both inside and outside the specimen for the recording of the inner and outer shells respectively, while the positions of the LVDT and strain gauges are displayed in Figure 2.

Figure 1: (a) Basic geometrical properties of specimens, (b) experimental set-up

Figure 2: Positions of (a) LVDTs for displacement measurement, (b) strain gauges for strain measurement

From the steel sheets used for the inner and the outer sandwich shells, 6 coupons were cut and subjected to tensile tests. The Young's modulus was found equal to 207 GPa and the yield stress, determined as the 0.2% proof stress, was equal to 301 MPa, both exhibiting negligible COV.

The core-filling mortar was selected as to be self-leveling, non-shrinking and of decent strength. Prismatic matrices were obtained from the mixes pumped into each sandwich specimen, in order to be tested under bending and axial compression later on. At the day of the experiments, the compressive strengths of the mortar mixes used in the two sandwich specimens were found equal to 24.5 MPa and 31.0 MPa, respectively, while their tensile strengths obtained from bending tests were 4.5 MPa and 5.0 MPa, respectively.

3. Numerical simulation

The simulation of the experimental process was realized using the ADINA finite element software [5]. Its main objective was the development of a model which, on the one hand, accurately captures the specimen's inherent nonlinearity, induced by the geometry, the materials and their interaction, and, on the other hand, is computationally as less demanding as possible, thus allowing for an upgrade to the actual size and load conditions of a wind turbine tower at a later stage.

3.1. Materials

As previously stated, cement-mortar was used in the experiments as a concrete substitute, since it would be impossible for the latter with its large aggregates to flow within the narrow core of the small-scaled specimens tested at this research stage. Nonetheless, mortar was numerically simulated by the concrete material model provided in ADINA, as this still incorporates the main properties required, namely cracking failure at relatively low tensile-stress levels and crushing followed by strain softening up to total failure at significantly higher values of compressive stress. Introducing the compressive and tensile strength values from the tests into the material model in question, results in the stress-strain curve of

Figure 3a, which is used in the simulation. The material's Poisson ratio was taken equal to 0.2 and its density equal to 1760 kg/m³, according to the product's technical data sheet.

Steel, as far as the inner and outer shells of the sandwich segment are concerned, was introduced into the model as a plastic multilinear material, defined by a simplified form of the true stress-strain curve obtained from the coupon tests. The curve in question is presented in Figure 3b. For the secondary steel parts of the specimen, which were designed with adequate overstrength to remain within the elastic region, a linear elastic material law was adopted. In any case, Poisson ratio for steel was taken equal to 0.3 and its density equal to 7850 kg/m³.

Figure 3: Material stress-strain curves for (a) mortar/concrete and (b) steel, incorporated into the model

3.2. Structural components and boundary conditions

The numerical model consisted of three parts: (i) the sandwich main specimen, comprising the inner and outer steel shells, the mortar core and one flange at each end, (ii) the conventional steel shell where the load was applied, also having a flange at each end, and (iii) the stub steel cylinder at the base of the cantilever, with a flange at one end and the end-plate for the connection with the testing frame at the other (see Figure 1 and Figure 4). A further decomposition of the above results in 4 steel shells, 5 steel flanges, 1 steel plate and 1 mortar core.

For the inner and outer steel tubes of the sandwich specimen, the conventional steel tube and the thick steel tube of the base, 4-node shell elements with 2x2 Gauss integration were utilized, suitable for both thin and thick shells. For the mortar core, the 5 flanges and the end plate, 8-node 3-D solid continuum elements with 2x2x2 Gauss integration were employed.

The welds connecting the steel tubes with the flanges and the end-plate were introduced into the model as shared nodes between the boundary elements of these components. At a first simulation-attempt, the same technique was also used for the bolted connections between adjacent flanges, as well as that between the end-plate and the testing frame. Since some differential rotation evidently took place during the experiments at the bolted connection between the end-plate and the testing frame, a second simulation was carried out, this time incorporating a spring element, connected to the end-plate by rigid links. Taking into consideration the horizontal and vertical displacements recorded by the LVDTs 3-5 of the end-plate (see Figure 2a), the point of rotation was determined and the rotational stiffness of the pertinent spring was estimated.

In order for the interaction of the mortar core with the inner and outer steel tubes, as well as with the steel flanges, to be simulated, the pertinent interfaces were modeled and appropriately paired as 3-D contact surfaces. A constraint-function method was adopted for enforcing the no-penetration and the frictional contact conditions. Friction between mortar and steel was modeled according to the standard Coulomb friction-law, with a friction coefficient of 0.65. A compliance factor, small enough to not affect the results of the analysis, was also introduced to the contact properties, allowing a negligible amount of penetration to take place between the interfaces for convergence purposes.

3.3. Loading conditions and analysis method

As was the case with the experimental procedure, the cantilever was loaded by means of lateral concentrated displacement, applied at the top of the conventional steel tube's end-flange (see Figure 1b and Figure 4b) in a quasi-static fashion. The dead load of the cantilever's components was also taken

into account in a mass-proportional manner. Full Newton-Raphson numerical method was utilized for the analysis. On account of the highly nonlinear nature of the problem, the automatic time-stepping algorithm of ADINA was employed for convergence facilitation. Tests of both GMNA and GMNIA analysis types resulted in similar responses of the model, indicating the problem's low sensitivity to imperfections. The analyses described herein are thus of the GMNA type.

Figure 4: (a) Main types of components and finite elements, (b) Complete numerical model of the cantilever

3.4. Validation of numerical results

In Figure 5a, the load-displacement curves referring to the load-application point of the two specimens and the ADINA model are plotted together. Clearly, the response of the numerical model is remarkably close to the experimental one, particularly with regard to the first specimen. It should be mentioned at this point that, although the two tested specimens performed similarly in terms of total strength, a difference between them is evident strain-wise, beginning to occur at approximately 70% of the peak load. This is a consequence of some inadvertent differential rotation, which was detected between flanges 3 and 4, connecting the sandwich shell with the conventional one.

Nevertheless, in both the experiment and the numerical analysis—including the second specimen, with the stiffness reduction due to the connection fault being disregarded—the cantilever's behavior remained linear up to approximately 80% of the peak load, at which point a first yielding of the steel tubes occurred, gradually bending the curve towards the peak. When the latter was reached, both sandwich specimens, as well as the numerical model, failed by means of local buckling at their compressed side. This became evident by an outward bulge of the outer steel tube (Figure 5b), at a distance of 90 mm, 60 mm and 25 mm from the base of the first specimen, the second specimen and the ADINA model, respectively. As can be observed in Figure 5a, convergence between the experimental and numerical results was maintained within the post-buckling region as well. The results obtained at the positions of LVDTs 1 and 2 were qualitatively similar with the ones discussed above. The distribution of von Mises stress on the two steel shells and the core at failure point is depicted in Figure 6a-c and reflects the above behavior.

In Figure 7, the load-strain curves of the numerical model and the two specimens are presented, pertaining to 6 of the experiment's strain-gauge positions. Generally speaking, the nature of the local-buckling failure mechanism itself makes strain convergence in the post-collapse region quite unlikely. Particularly, given that the exact position of local buckling naturally differed between the three cases, strains at the strain-gauge positions in that area could not be the same between them either. Moreover, some minor installation errors and the strain-gauges' inherent susceptibility to them, led to additional divergence, mostly regarding the results of the second experiment. However, qualitatively and in some cases quantitatively as well, the experimental strain results and the numerical ones are generally in good agreement with each other and accurately describe the overall behavior of the sandwich shells. For example, the curves of Figure 7a—referring to the compressed side, at 30 mm from the base of the outer and the inner steel shell respectively—clearly point out the pre-mentioned local buckling of the second

specimen and the numerical model near that area, oppositely to the first specimen which buckled at a higher distance from the base, thus exhibiting much lower strains. On the other hand, at 80 mm from the base (Figure 7b), significantly higher strains are observed regarding the first specimen, which bulged outwards near that area. Furthermore, a comparison between the two plots of Figure 7a, as well as the two plots of Figure 7b, indicates that the inner and outer shells behaved similarly and thus cooperated satisfactorily. Concerning the second specimen, higher strain levels of the inner shell at 30 mm, compared to those at 80 mm, point out a slightly different local buckling position of the inner and the outer shell, which in turn is probably related to a diagonal shear failure of the core. In Figure 7c, the load-strain curves at mid-height of the inner shell's cross section, where the neutral axis initially lay, as well as those at 45 mm below mid-height, are presented for the numerical model and the second specimen (strain gauges at this area were not installed on the first specimen). The experimental strains point out a gradual transition of the neutral axis towards the compressed side of the specimen. This evidences the core's contribution to the cross section, since it is mortar's dissimilar behavior under compression and tension that causes this development. This was hardly the case with the numerical model, though, as its neutral axis only slightly moved towards the compressed side, possibly indicating lower exploitation of mortar's tensile capacity at the experiment, in comparison with the numerical simulation.

Figure 5: (a) Load-displacement curves of the two specimens and the numerical model at the load-application point, (b) outward-folding failure mechanism of the specimen and the numerical model

Figure 6: Post-buckling distribution of von Mises stress on (a) the outer shell, (b) the inner shell and (c) the core

4. Parametric study

In order for the influence of the main factors characterizing a sandwich tower to be investigated, a series of parametric analyses based on the validated numerical model was carried out, with respect to thickness of the three layers, material qualities and loading conditions. Regarding the thickness of the core and the inner and outer shells, the former varied between 4 mm and 22 mm, while the latter took values between 2 mm and 8 mm, the changes taking place symmetrically with respect to the core's mid-line, that is to say half inwards and half outwards. Material-wise, different steel qualities —namely S235, S275, S355, S420 and S450— were incorporated into the simulation, in the simplified form of a bilinear material model with hardening. Various mortar/concrete qualities were also tested, following the stress-strain curve of Figure 3b and differing with each other in terms of ultimate compressive load, the latter taking values from 15 MPa to 55 MPa. As far as load conditions are concerned, along with the lateral displacement already imposed, constant axial compression, equally distributed at the free end of the cantilever structure, was additionally applied, resembling a wind turbine nacelle's dead load. A sample of the pertinent results is demonstrated in Figure 8a-d.

Figure 7: Experimental and numerical load-strain curves of the sandwich shell (a) at its compressed side, 30 mm from the base, (b) at its compressed side, 80 mm from the base and (c) at the neutral-axis area

Figure 8: Effect of (a) inner and outer shells' thickness, (b) core thickness, (c) steel quality and (d) core existence on model's behavior

Through the analyses in question, it was observed that the thickness of the outer and inner steel shells significantly affected the capacity of the structure, the two being directly proportional. On the other hand, the thickness of the mortar/concrete core had a minor impact on the performance, contributing slightly more at thicknesses around 16 mm. Steel quality proved to be a significant factor for the capacity of the sandwich shell, as an almost directly proportional relation was observed between steel quality and strength. On the contrary, mortar quality had negligible effect on structure's behavior. The combination of axial and bending loads did not considerably affect the performance in a qualitative manner. Although mortar/concrete might be expected to increasingly contribute to the strength of the sandwich shell as axially compressive loads become higher, it seems that, as far as this specific structure is concerned, geometrical nonlinearity is the predominant factor, leading to local buckling phenomena before mortar's compressive strength can be exploited. This might also partially account for a comparison between a mortar/concrete-filled core and an empty core resulting in only a marginal increase in strength in the case of the former, as presented in Figure 8d. It is noteworthy nonetheless that, regarding the same comparison, the gain in ductility due to the filled core was apparently higher.

5. Conclusions

Finite element modeling and corresponding nonlinear analysis of steel-concrete-steel sandwich shells subjected to bending, representing scaled wind turbine towers, have been presented and were found to satisfactorily simulate the response, as evidenced by the good agreement of the numerical results with experimental tests that had been previously performed by the authors. The critical failure mode was found to be local buckling for both the specimens and the numerical models. Results in terms of displacements, stresses and strains indicate that nonlinearities derived from the geometry, the materials and their composite interaction were well captured by the modelling features employed. The parametric numerical analyses denoted the predominant role of steel in the behavior of the structure, as both material quality and thickness of the pertinent inner and outer shells significantly affected load-bearing capacity. Mortar/concrete as core material appeared to be of secondary importance as far as the structure's strength is concerned. Overall, however, the sandwich shell was found to exhibit adequate composite action, which enhanced its ductility, as clearly indicated by a comparison with an empty-core equivalent.

Acknowledgements

This research has been supported by the OptArch project: "Optimization Driven Architectural Design of Structures" (No: 689983) belonging to the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) Research and Innovation Staff Exchange (RISE) H2020-MSCA-RISE-2015.

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